

Remembrane: A Shape Changing Adaptive Structure

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Abstract. This paper presents a research on adaptive kinetic structures using shape memory alloys as actuators. The target of the research is designing and building an efficient kinetic structural system that could be potentially applied at an architectural scale. The project is based on the study of tensegrity and pantograph structures as a starting point to develop multiple digital and physical models of different structural systems that can be controllably moved. The result of this design process is a performative prototype that is controllable through a web-based interface. The main contribution of this project is not any of the presented parts by themselves but the integration of all of them in the creation of a new adaptive system that allows us to envision a novel way of designing, building and experiencing architecture in a dynamic and efficient way.

Keywords: Responsive Structures, Kinetic Structures, Adaptive Systems, User Interaction, Structural Optimization

1 Introduction

Understanding the significant need of generating the production of responsive construction systems, the scope of the paper is to present a case study on computed matter, exploring shape memory adaptive structures to be applied at architectural scale. The project implements shape memory alloys, digital content, fabrication and user interfaces to set up an intelligent responsive structural system that can be applied in different architectural scales. Shape memory alloys are not new and have been extensively used previously for a number of kinetic prototypes. The novel aspect of the present research is the overlapping of computational design and simulations, physical computing and user interfaces in the implementation of dynamic systems (user-environment) in the architectural scale.

Remembrane is an exploration of applying shape memory alloys to create a big scale adaptive kinetic pantograph-tensegrity structure that could adapt to environmental changes and be easily controlled by users through a user-friendly interface. The research focus has been placed on the structural design following the

material properties and allowing users to be the ultimate decision makers of the performance of the structure. The developed prototype investigates the use of springs made of Nitinol (a shape memory alloy) as linear actuators. The project avoided from the beginning the use of centralized heavy motors to move the system and focused on developing a distributed system of lightweight actuators (nitinol springs) embedded into the structure that allow a much more precise control of the shape and a much more energy efficient movement.

The interaction with the structure and the different ways of controlling it have also been an essential aspect of the project. Easy manual control of the shape and automatic autonomous performance of the system had to be combined in order to achieve a truly intelligent and efficient interaction. Both ideas were at the starting point of the design of the user interface. The final prototype of the research is a real scale performative kinetic structure. The prototype has been deliberately left without a specific function in order to allow us to envision an endless number of potential applications: from adaptive partition solutions to environmentally responsive roofs, to morphing facades and changing urban elements (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Different applications of adaptive structures

2 Background

Kinetic and adaptive structures have been part of the architectural discourse for decades, but recent technological advancements have made them much more feasible. From academic research to real built structures motion has now become an integral part of architectural design.

The adaptive affordances of kinetic structures have been debated in architectural research for more than a decade (Senagala, 2005). The issues of automation and control have been proved instrumental in the development of kinetic, responsive and adaptive structures and their contribution towards a ‘smart architecture’. A wide variety of strategies in construction and automation of kinetic, robotic and complex systems mechanisms has been employed to achieve transformability and adaptability in engineering and architecture (Sanchez del Valle, 2005). Under this scope digital prototyping and simulation has always been a key component in the development of these strategies. Moreover, the issues of user control and interaction have also been rigorously studied and proposed as inevitable components of human perception and engagement with dynamic structures and architectural spaces (Michael & Allyn, 2012). In this study, we are proposing a novel adaptive system that aims to incorporating all of the above. Specifically, the project implements a kinetic mechanism, i.e. shape memory alloys, digital content, fabrication and user interfaces to set up a responsive structural system that can be applied across different architectural scales.

As mentioned, kinetic structures are not new in architecture. They have been envisioned and developed for decades and can be categorized according to their typology, motivation, type and mechanical analysis of the kinetic mechanism (Ron & Weissenbock, 2013). Various structural, behavioral and physiological adaptation agendas have been employed for a variety of design objectives, including environmental control, energy generation, conservation and transport and usage principles as well as material property based changes per component (Biloria &

Sumini, 2009). As mentioned, the proposed system has been deliberately proposed without a prescribed application as it is envisioned as an open-ended system that aims to be the basis for future applications of kinetic structures based on shape memory alloys.

Shape memory alloys are certainly not novel technology as they have been commercially available for decades, however their use in architectures is not very widespread although there has been a number of studies that has demonstrated their potential in architectural applications. Nickel Titanium Shape Memory Alloys have been implemented in small scale prototypes to demonstrate their ability to configure and reconfigure spatial volumes (Villalon, 2007). Our study uses Nitinol springs in the form of a lightweight distributed system of actuation of a larger scale structure. Nitinol springs have also been implemented for the investigation of surface movement through controlled and repeatable deformation of a composite structure of an art installation demonstrating their potential in further application of architectural scope (Esquivel et al, 2013). Shape memory polymers (SMP) have also been implemented in small scale prototypes in lightweight deployable structure and have also demonstrated the potential of shape-changing materials in architectural scale and scope.

As previously stated the main contribution of this project lies on the integration of all aforementioned aspects of fabrication, control and automation for the development of an open ended kinetic system that can form the basis of further architectural applications

3 Methods

3.1 Actuators

The first development step was to test different actuators and assess them in terms of their resistance, lifespan and light-weightness. Shape memory alloys (in particular Nitinol) were the selected solution because they are relatively powerful and lightweight. These two characteristics make them very suitable for an actuation system that is embedded into the structure and distributed throughout its different parts. Nitinol wires are flexible at normal air temperature and they go back to a “saved shape” when heated above the transformation temperature (70 °C for the used wires). This transformation process can be used to create an actuator and enhanced by shaping the wires into springs. To save a specific shape, the Nitinol wire has to be fixed in the desired position and heated between 400°C and 800°C for around 5 min and immediately cooled down (Fig. 2).

Several experiments were carried out to test the material resistance and strength in order to optimize the structure and its movement. Moreover, a proper heating system had to be developed to optimize the reaction time as well as to avoid material damages, trying to make the solution reliable and stable. The tests proved the material capacity to lift certain weight when heated. All the experimentations were carried out with the same environmental conditions and interpolated to obtain a reliable dataset.

Fig. 2. Nitinol – shaped into springs, stretched and reshaped by heat

Fig. 3. Nitinol springs strength test

The results underline a relationship of direct proportionality between spring's shrink and loads (Fig. 3). However, tests have highlighted how unstable the material is if not properly heated. Therefore, to avoid any material damages, a proper and controlled heating system had to be designed. Activating Nitinol using DC current with the proper amount of electricity allows a homogeneous and precise heating. However, DC current could easily overheat and damage the Nitinol wire. To limit these potential material damages a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) circuit was developed. Using PWM has several advantages: it turns the current on and off to the wire very quickly and this power oscillation allows to keep heating the wire while avoiding damage to the material's crystalline structure. Moreover, by modulating the "oscillation" period, the shrink time can be easily controlled.

After several tests and physical models, springs made of 1 mm thick Nitinol were used for the prototypes because they presented appropriate strength for the scale that

was being studied. The electronic circuit designed to control these Nitinol wires was composed by an Arduino board and four transistors that controlled the amount of current released in each Nitinol wire (Fig. 4). In the final prototype a 14V power supply was used and each transistor released 4,67A to its corresponding Nitinol line (made of four 650 mm long and 1.0 mm thick cables, shaped as springs).

Fig. 4. Electronic circuit

3.2 Structure

After studying the properties of Nitinol and understanding its advantages and limitations as an actuator, the actual skeleton of the structure had to be explored. Therefore, the next step was a series of tests focused on geometric principles and structural systems that allow kinetic behaviour. Each system design iteration was simulated to understand and predict its behaviour. The software that was used was *Kangaroo*, a plug-in for *Grasshopper* for *Rhinoceros 3D*. Most of the explored systems can be understood with an analogy to the human body in which the structure itself, the bones, consist of rigid elements (bars) and the muscles, the Nitinol wires, take care of the movement.

There are 2 structural/geometrical principles that were further studied and served as a base for the final design of the system: pantographs and tensegrities. The pantograph mechanisms are able to expand or compress in a vector perpendicularly to the actuating vector. Pantographs are made of crisscrossing sticks and their main advantage is their capacity to achieve big expansions with a small actuation movement. They are also lightweight structures and they introduce the idea of deploy ability (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Pantograph inspired structure – actuation with a motor

Tensegrity structures are systems in which tensile and compressive elements are harmoniously working in complement towards equilibrium. They are visually recognizable with the individual compressive elements held into its place in space by tensile elements that form a continuous network. The integrity of the structure is taken care by the tensile members and not the compressive ones. Therefore, tensegrities are light and, on paper, efficient if its assembly complexity is ignored. Tensegrities are easily convertible to kinetic structures by replacing some of the tensile elements (cables) by linear actuators.

Both pantograph and tensegrity principles have been used for the development of a vast variety of structural systems that can be divided into two main groups: the linear systems and the surface systems (space frames). The linear systems behave like towers that can bend in any direction (like a finger) by locally controlling the actuators (Fig. 6). The linear systems are relatively easy to move and control but they cannot be directly applied as an architectural structure, they always need to be part of another system.

Fig. 6. Pseudo-tensegrity prototype controlled by a digital interface

The surface systems are space frame structures that can be shaped in many different ways (Fig. 7). Surface systems are much more interesting for an architectural application than the linear ones because they can become by themselves architectural elements (partitions, facades, roofs, canopies etc.). They are able to adopt an endless number of shapes and positions to adapt to environmental conditions and user's needs (Fig. 8). Some of the surface systems that were digitally tested presented the ability to bend in multiple directions (double curvature) (Fig. 9). However, a single curvature behaviour was chosen as the most appropriate one to develop in order to avoid an overly complex structure.

Fig. 7. Pseudo-tensegrity prototype controlled by a digital interface

Fig. 8. Digital simulations of a pseudo-tensegrity space-frame structure with control of local cables

Fig. 9. Surface system with double curvature

3.3 Remembrane 1.0

The geometrical system that presented the best performance was a diagrid pantograph with pseudo-tensegrity principles. Wood pieces with flexible plastic joints and a diagonal network of Nitinol springs were the main components of the prototype (*Remembrane 1.0*) (Fig. 10). The bending of the surface is provoked by the contraction of the Nitinol springs when they are heated. This first prototype was a significant step in the study, however, there were four main aspects that had to be improved or developed: improving the actuation and creating a locking system, reducing the weight of the structure, designing and building a skin and programming a user interface.

Fig. 10. 1st performative prototype – *Remembrane 1.0* – base skeleton and nitinol springs

The actuation system was improved by placing the Nitinol actuators in vertical lines and adding a diagonal network of tensioned coil springs and cables that help stabilize the structure (Fig. 11). The diagonal network also allows to lock the structure in any position thanks to a locking mechanism integrated within the structural components. When the system is locked, a piece of folded plastic (polypropylene) pushes two small elements that block the diagonal cables connected to the structure. A small Nitinol spring is connected to the element that blocks the cables. If the Nitinol is heated, it contracts and moves the plastic pieces, releasing the cables and allowing the whole structure to move freely (Fig. 12). Thanks to the locking system the Nitinol springs do not need to be constantly electrified to maintain a certain position and the system becomes much more efficient in terms of energy consumption and movement control.

The expansion of tensioned coil springs is proportional to the system movement: the more the structure bends, the stronger the force these springs apply to the system (Fig. 13). This force counters gravity and helps to stabilize the entire structure. Consequently, the actuators need less force to move the structure. In fact, the final solution uses 41,26% less Nitinol than the previous versions, and 75% less energy.

Fig. 11. Actuating Nitinol springs (Left) & Cables with tensioned coil springs (right)

Fig. 12. Local stabilization device using Nitinol to release friction

Fig. 13. System devices coordination for movement and stabilization

3.4 Structural Optimization

The structural optimization has been an essential step to maximize the lightweight performance of the structure. In order to minimize the system weight without modifying its strength, a topological optimization process has been carried out. This analysis has generated an important mass reduction (about 52%). To perform the structural analysis, *Karamba*, - a parametric structural engineering plugin for *Grasshopper* for *Rhinoceros3D* - has been used (Fig. 14). Thanks to this tool, the structure has been checked from a structural point of view, and the shape of each element has been informed according to the software results, minimizing the material quantity and improving the general system behavior (Fig. 15).

By reducing the structure weight, Nitinol springs need less force (and electricity) to move the structure. Moreover, each joint has been informed by the analysis optimizing its shape and minimizing deformations (Fig. 16).

Fig. 14. Analyzing structural component for optimization

Fig. 15. Structural components after optimization with reduced material

Fig. 16. Remembrance 2.0 - base structure with actuators and wirings

3.5 Skin

The structure has been mainly developed as skeletal system, conjunctionally with flexible joints and Nitinol springs acting as muscles pulling on them. As a complex assemblage of multiple components, a skin was necessary to contain the whole within one visual entity; a continuous surface as an architectural boundary, and to protect the mechanics from exterior elements such as water, corrosion and physical contact (Fig. 17). The protection goes in the other way to protect the users from the sharp components, the electrical current running through the wires and the heat generated to actuate the Nitinol springs.

It is an added skin over a lightweight skeleton; choice of material or system can be flexible, according to the use of the structure. However, the chosen material was a thin sheet of silicone, which is known to withstand heat, harsh chemicals, electric current, and resist to a great expansion, since the structure is meant to be deformed and transformed several times. It also offers a great translucency to allow the light to pass through, if its use is to create a space requiring natural light. The industry offers silicones with different transparency and elasticity, which make it an interesting choice, but also quite experimental for our application.

Fig. 17. Elastic skin as layer of protection

The elastic membrane is attached to the pantograph joints while floating bar components push the skin towards outside, creating a morphing tensile landscape on the surface and emphasizing the tensegrity character of the structure. This allows stabilizing the structure by adding extra surficial tension. Using this principle and these bars being longer than the thickness of the structure, the overall skin is already under moderate tension while straight. This bar system becomes helpful especially when the structure bends; one side of the skin experiences more tension than the other. The tensioned side pushes the floating bars towards the other, less tensioned, side hence soothing forces avoiding wrinkles on one side and hypertension on the other side in order to avoid the risk of skin rupture (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18. Damping system for tensile skin using bars

3.6 User Interface

The interaction between the users and the *Remembrance* is one of the most important parts of the project. A truly innovative responsive kinetic system has to be easily controllable but also intelligent enough to make its own decisions. In order to achieve that, a complex interaction system had to be designed. The system has two possible ways of interacting: interface mode (the user sends orders through the user interface) and sensing mode (the structure reacts to the sensors' inputs) (Fig. 19).

To make this complex interaction as easy as possible a user-friendly web based interface has been designed. A web application has the huge advantage of being accessible by any device that can support a web browser. This means that any computer, smartphone or tablet can be used to run the user interface and no special software or hardware is needed. The interface has been developed in order to not only send orders to the prototype but also to visualize the information measured by the sensors installed on the structure (Fig. 20). Therefore, there is a bidirectional communication with the *Remembrance*. Four different scripting languages have been used to develop the application: Html, Css, JavaScript and Processing.

Fig. 19. Data input and output cycle through several agents

To physically interact with the structure a microcontroller was needed. The microcontroller acts as an intermediate between the web application and the prototype. The most extended and easy to use microcontroller is the Arduino and among all the Arduino models the Yun was chosen because it can connect to the internet using wifi and, therefore, it allows to interact with the web application wirelessly. The actual interaction with the *Remembrance* takes place at the input and output pins of the microcontroller. The input signals come from 2 proximity sensors (one in each side of the structure) and 1 accelerometer that measure the inclination. The output signals go to the network of actuators, to the locking / unlocking system and to the 2 LEDs that show the status of the structure.

The Graphic User Interface has been carefully designed to allow an easy and efficient interaction between the user and the *Remembrance*. It is based on interactive graphics that make the whole communication process very intuitive. The most important element of the interface is the interactive 2D diagram. It can be reshaped just by touching the screen of a tablet/smartphone (or clicking and dragging on a computer) and it automatically sends the necessary information to shape the structure in the same way (Fig. 22). The 2D diagram is complemented by 2 other elements: a visualization of the real inclination of the structure measured by the accelerometer (Fig. 21) and a visualization of the distance to obstacles measured by the 2 proximity sensors. The 2D diagram is, therefore, a tool to send instructions but also a tool to understand the current state of the prototype. The button under the diagram is used to lock or unlock the structure. On top of the 2D diagram there is a 3D previsualization of the structure. On the top left corner of the interface there is a button that allows the user to switch between interface control mode and sensing mode. In the interface-mode the structure reacts only to the instructions sent through the interface. On the other hand, in the sensing mode, the prototype performs autonomously according to

the sensors' inputs. In fact, it behaves according to a set of rules that have been pre-programmed. The final prototype has a very basic set of rules: when the proximity sensor detects that something is very close, the structure bends to the opposite side (Fig. 23). This simple behavior has the purpose of illustrating some kind of autonomous behavior that could be further developed. On the left side of the user interface there are different numbers that are continuously updated. These values are the data from the sensors and the length of all the actuators of the structure.

Fig. 20. User Interface on a wireless device

Fig. 21. User Interface wirelessly indicating current curvature

Fig. 22. Wireless control via user interface

Fig. 23. Autonomous response via proximity sensor

4 Results and Discussion

All the digital and physical explorations have led to a better understanding of the possibilities and the limitations of the systems that have been designed. Lightweight responsive kinetic structures based on pantograph and tensegrity principles with a distributed system of Nitinol actuators have been proven to be feasible. Moreover, the final version of the *Remembrance* has become not only a performative kinetic prototype, but also a demonstration of new ways of user interaction and an exploration on basic autonomous performance. However, the *Remembrance* prototype presents two important weaknesses that could limit its further development into architectural elements.

The first big limitation is the use of Nitinol as actuator. Nitinol is definitely an appropriate material for lightweight linear actuators. However, in the architectural scale, Nitinol presents two major disadvantages: it needs a big amount of electricity to reach the temperature in which it actuates and it has significant restrictions in terms of strength when using small sections. Another important aspect to reconsider is the number of elements of the prototype. After every test that was carried out many problems appeared. In general, the problems were solved by refining the existing

components but also adding more elements to the structure. The result has been a highly complex prototype (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24. Remembrance 2.0 in action

5 Conclusion

This study ends with a strong belief in the future of lightweight responsive kinetic structures. We envision that they are the evolution of the current architecture and they will radically change the way that spaces are experienced. These structures have evident advantages in terms of energy performance and adaptability to the needs of the users. Furthermore, there is already available technology to create interactive structures with embedded artificial intelligence. However, it is absolutely necessary to understand the limitations of the systems and materials that have been tested in order to set the basis for future research on adaptable kinetic structures.

New ways of heating the Nitinol springs should definitely be explored. A passive system using the solar radiation in a controlled way to heat the Nitinol wires is surely an interesting future research line. The limitation in terms of strength of the Nitinol springs could be solved by increasing the section of the wires. However, the current cost of big Nitinol wires makes them unsuitable for real architectural structures. Nevertheless, it is not unreasonable to think that in the near future Nitinol will become much more affordable and it will be a common material in the construction industry.

As mentioned before, the big amount of elements in the final system is one of its major weaknesses. The challenge now is not to keep adding complexity but to

simplify the whole system to the point that the same performance is achieved with less and simpler components. Continuing this research following the stated guidelines would surely lead to a better and more energy-efficient kinetic structure to be applied in the construction of the architectural spaces for the contemporary world.

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